

Synthesis and Antifungal Activity of Bisphenolic Derivatives

GIRIJA SUBRAMANIAM*, R. SAVITHRI and SIVANESWARI THAMBIPILLAI

Department of Chemistry, Sri Sarada College, Salem-636 016

Manuscript received 17 January 1989, accepted 20 June 1989

Hitherto unreported dicinnamates and dioxyacetic acids of the known fungicides, 4,4'-isopropylidenebisphenol and 4,4'-cyclohexylidenebisphenol were synthesised and characterised by spectral techniques. Their antifungal activity against the vascular wilt pathogenic fungus *Fusarium oxysporum* was determined.

VARIOUS bisphenols have been shown to be effective fungicides specifically against mildew preventives on cotton fabric¹ and against the fungi that cause peach brown rot². Many of them also exhibit antibacterial³ and coccidial⁴ activities. However, most of the phenolic compounds suffer from the disadvantage of being toxic to the host cells. One way of overcoming this phytotoxicity is to convert the phenolic function to an easily hydrolysable functionality like ester. This helps the slow release of phenol and avoids a local high concentration that is toxic to the host cells. Literature survey reveals that this aspect is not explored extensively. There has been only two reports^{1,5} to date on the effect of derivatisation of some chlorobisphenols and their antifungal activity.

Since more than 20% of this reported plant diseases were fungal in origin⁶, this work was initiated with the aim of designing less toxic but more potent antifungal derivatives of bisphenols, specifically to be tested against plant pathogenic fungi. This paper describes the syntheses and preliminary *in vitro* screening of these compounds against *Fusarium oxysporum*, a major component of the fungal flora of the most cultivated soils.

1, 2; R = H
1a, 2a; R = COCH = CHC₆H₅
1b, 2b; R = COC₆H₄ (o-OH)
1c, 2c; R = CH₂COOH
2d; R = CH₃

Experimental

4,4'-Isopropylidenebisphenol (1): It was synthesised according to the reported procedure⁷, m.p.

138–45° (lit. 146–53°); $\nu_{\max}$ (KBr) 3 360, 2 980, 1 620, 1 610 and 830 cm⁻¹; ¹H nmr (CDCl₃) δ 8.35 (2H, s, OH), 6.8–6.3 (8H, m, Ph) and 1.5 (6H, s, Me); ¹³C nmr δ (acetone-d₆) 155.51, 142.47, 128.05, 115.0, 41.72 and 31.18.

4,4'-Cyclohexylidenebisphenol (2): It was synthesised by the reported procedure⁸, m.p. 182–84° (lit.⁹ 183–85°); $\nu_{\max}$ (KBr) 3 200, 2 980, 1 620, 1 600 and 830 cm⁻¹; ¹H nmr δ (CDCl₃) 8.35 (2H, s, OH), 6.8–6.3 (8H, m, Ph), 2.1 (4H, m) and 1.45 (6H, m); ¹³C nmr δ (acetone-d₆) 155.37, 140.49, 128.49, 115.35, 45.26, 32.79, 26.86 and 23.42.

4,4'-Isopropylidenebisphenyldicinnamate (1a): Cinnamoyl chloride (prepared by refluxing together cinnamic acid and thionyl chloride) and 1 were refluxed at 70–5° till the completion of the reaction. The crude solid was washed with water and recrystallised from acetone to give white crystals (87.6%), m.p. 167–69°; $\nu_{\max}$ (KBr) 2 980, 1 700, 1 500, 975 and 850 cm⁻¹; ¹H nmr δ (CDCl₃) 7.55–7.44 (1H, d, =CH), 7.2–6.4 (18H, m, Ar), 6.35–6.15 (1H, d, =CH) and 1.6 (6H, s, Me); ¹³C nmr δ (DMSO-d₆) 164.60, 148.23, 147.40, 146.23, 136.73, 133.76, 128.88, 128.52, 122.43, 121.14, 117.17, 41.96 and 30.42.

4,4'-Cyclohexylidenebisphenyldicinnamate (2a): It is synthesised by the same procedure used for 1a, m.p. 145–48°; $\nu_{\max}$ (KBr) 2 980, 1 730, 1 510, 980 and 865 cm⁻¹; ¹H nmr δ (CDCl₃) 7.55–7.3 (1H, d, =CH), 7.25–6.45 (18H, m, Ar), 6.45–6.25 (1H, s, =CH), 2.05 (4H, m), 1.4 (6H, m); ¹³C nmr δ (DMSO-d₆) 164.26, 142.98, 148.20, 145.2, 133.70, 130.72, 128.80, 128.51, 127.71, 121.32, 117.17, 45.07, 36.20, 25.81 and 22.43.

4,4'-Isopropylidenebisphenyldisalicylate (1b): It was prepared as 1a, m.p. 143–45°; $\nu_{\max}$ (KBr) 3 220, 1 710, 1 615 and 840 cm⁻¹; ¹H nmr δ (CDCl₃) 10.2 (2H, s, OH), 8.6–8.5, 7.15–6.45 (18H, m, Ar) and 1.6 (3H, s, CH₃); ¹³C nmr δ (DMSO-d₆) 162.59, 149.10, 148.92, 137.06, 130.93,

*Present address: Department of Chemistry, University of Toledo, Toledo, Ohio-43606, U.S.A.

128.44, 121.87, 120.11, 118.08, 112.59, 42.98 and 30.86.

4,4'-Cyclohexylidenebisphenyldisalicylate (2b): It was prepared as 1a, m.p. 155–57°; $\nu_{\max}$ (KBr) 3 150, 2 920, 1 700, 1 625 and 840 cm^{-1} ; ^1H nmr δ (CDCl_3) 10.2 (2H, s, OH) 8.75–8.6, 7.8–7.65 (18H, m, Ar), 2.15 (4H, m) and 1.4 (6H, m).

4,4'-Cyclohexylidenebisphenyldioxyacetic acid (2c): Phenol (1 g, 4.3 mmol) and chloroacetic acid was dissolved in sodium hydroxide and refluxed at 100° for 1 h, then diluted with water, acidified and ether-extracted. The ether layer was again extracted with sodium carbonate solution (5%; 25 ml), acidified and the crude acid filtered. Recrystallisation from water gave the pure acid, m.p. 152–55; $\nu_{\max}$ (KBr) 3 100–2 900, 1 725, 1 645 and 830 cm^{-1} ; ^1H nmr δ (DMSO-d_6) 6.9–5.9 (8H, m, Ar), 4.2 (4H, s, OCH_2) and 1.3 (6H, s, Me); ^{13}C nmr δ (DMSO-d_6) 168.86, 158.50, 144.15, 128.12, 114.42, 65.11, 41.02 and 31.00.

4,4'-Cyclohexylidenebisphenyldioxyacetic acid (2e): It was prepared by using the procedure for 1c, m.p. 135–37°; $\nu_{\max}$ (KBr) 3 100–2 900, 1 720, 1 615 and 830 cm^{-1} ; ^1H nmr δ (DMSO-d_6) 7.0–6.1 (8H, m, Ar), 4.4 (4H, s, OCH_2), 2.1 (4H, m) and 1.4 (6H, m).

4,4'-Cyclohexylidenebisphenoxymethane (2d): It was prepared by the reaction of an alkaline solution of dimethyl sulphate with 2. Work up and extraction gave an oil which solidified on cooling in an ice-bath, ^1H nmr δ (CDCl_3) 6.0–5.25 (8H, m, Ar), 3.0–2.8 (6H, s, CH_2) and 2.0–1.1 (10H, m, cyclohexyl); ^{13}C nmr δ (CDCl_3) 156.95, 141.01, 113.41, 55.08, 44.95, 37.35, 26.36 and 22.88.

Antifungal activity: Compounds 2, 2a–2d were tested for their activity against *Fusarium oxysporum* by filter paper disc method. The fungus was allowed to sporulate in potato-dextrose-agar slants. Spore suspension was prepared by transferring the spores to sterile test tubes with sterile distilled water, and by further dilution with sterile water. The spore suspension (0.5 ml) was transferred to petri-dish followed by the medium, avoiding all possible contaminations. Sterile paper discs (dia. 5 mm) were soaked in the test solutions (50, 25 and 10 ppm solutions) and carefully placed in the set medium by sterile needles and incubated at 37°. The effect of the chemicals was studied by measuring the diameter of the clear zone around the discs.

Results and Discussion

Acid-catalysed condensation of phenol and the appropriate carbonyl compound yielded the desired phenol in good yield. The compounds were

characterised by their mass, ir, proton and carbon nmr spectra. Their esters were prepared by the direct reaction of phenol with the corresponding acid chloride. This method seems to be more effective on a small scale as is done here in getting the pure product than the one described in the literature¹⁰. The cinnamate esters and dioxyacetic acids of both 4,4'-isopropylidenebisphenol (1) and 4,4'-cyclohexylidenebisphenol (2) are synthesised for the first time.

All the compounds were tested for their antifungal action against the common fungi that grows on stale bread. These preliminary results showed all the compounds to be active; the derivatives of 2 seem to be even more potent than the parent phenol itself. This prompted us to screen 2 and its derivatives against the plant pathogen *Fusarium oxysporum*, rather than 1 and its derivatives. Table 1 summarises the results of this assay.

TABLE 1 – ANTIFUNGAL ACTIVITY DATA OF 2 AND ITS DERIVATIVES

Comp. no.	Zone of inhibition (dia. in mm)		
	50 ppm	25 ppm	10 ppm
2	35	25	15
2a	30	10	3
2b	25	10	3
2c	—	—	—
2d	—	—	—

The results show the dimethyl ether (2c) and the dioxyacetic acid (2d) to be inactive even at the highest concentration level used, whereas both the esters (2a and 2b) are active even at the minimum concentration level used. These results are very significant in that it hints at the active core of these fungicides. Ether linkage is known to be very inert towards hydrolytic cleavage, unlike esters. The activity found among esters may be due to the fact that they release the phenol – 'the active component' – by slow hydrolysis. This also explains the lower potency of these esters relative to 2 – for, at a given concentration, the local concentration of phenol available from esters will be much lower than from 2 itself. It is also worth noting that 2b, the salicylate ester, has a free phenolic group at the *ortho* position and in spite of it, is less active than 2. This, again points out that the activity is specifically due to the bisphenolic group rather than any other phenolic group in the molecule.

These preliminary results are encouraging and suggest that 2b and 2a could be less toxic without losing their potency and could be used effectively against diseases. Further evaluations relating to their phytotoxicity are to be done before they would be of any practical value.

References

1. P. B. MARSH, M. L. BUTLER and B. S. CLARK, *Ind. Eng. Chem.*, 1940, 41, 2176.
2. M. C. GOLDSWORTHY and S. I. GERTER, *Plant Disease Rep, Suppl.*, 1949, 182, 89.
3. M. KOJI, *Chem. Abstr.*, 1953, 47, 1884.
4. J. E. JOHNSON, JR. and D. R. MUSSELL, US Pat. 2 535 014/1950 (*Chem. Abstr.*, 1951, 45, 2635, 4412).
5. C. H. ARNDT, *Phytopathology*, 1948, 38, 978.
6. G. RANGASWAMI, "Diseases of Crop Plants in India", 2nd. ed., Prentice-Hall, New Delhi, p. 471.
7. P. H. DEMING and H. DANNENBERG, US Pat. 2 669 585/1954 (*Chem. Abstr.*, 1955, 49, 2499).
8. M. E. MCGREAL, V. NIEDERL and J. B. NIEDRL, *J. Am. Chem. Soc.*, 1939, 61, 345.
9. A. ZINKE and E. ZIEGLER, *J. Prakt. Chem.*, 1940, 156 169.
10. F. BRYNER and A. J. DIETZLER, US Pat. 3 041 370/1962 (*Chem. Abstr.*, 1962, 57, 13681).